

CATALYTIC FORMATION OF METHANE FROM CARBON MONOXIDE AND HYDROGEN. PART V. A STUDY OF THE PROMOTER EFFECT UPON NICKEL CATALYST.

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The reduction of nickel catalyst at a temperature of 300° is incomplete when prepared from a very pure sample of nickel acetate. Addition of a small quantity of a mixture of cerium nitrate and ammonium vanadate or of cerium nitrate and chromium acetate to the nickel acetate helps in bringing about a more thorough reduction. Thus catalysis of the reaction $2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2 = \text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4$ is directly accelerated by them. Whether there is any direct beneficial effect of the promoters cannot be said at this stage.

Very often small quantities of promoters are added to increase the activity of a catalyst. It is believed that the joint effect of the catalyst material and the promoters somehow accelerates a reaction to a greater extent than if the catalyst were used alone. But up till now very little work has been done to show that these added promoters influence the actual physical and chemical processes through which the catalyst passes in course of its preparation, apart from their direct effect if any upon the reaction which the catalyst is to accelerate. It may be, that in certain cases, they influence both the condition of preparation of the catalyst as well as its direct action. But there may also be cases where only one of these factors is operative. Again a substance, which favourably affects the one, may have an adverse influence upon the other. Ingredients which adversely affect the former will yield, however, a catalyst of low activity or of none. In this case, the poisoning effect on the catalytic reaction is only indirect. In the same way the promoter effect may be only an indirect one. It, therefore, follows that a theory of promoter action and of poisoning cannot be correctly developed unless one knows which of the above factors is actually affected by the promoter or poison, as the case may be.

Armstrong and Hilditch (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A103**, 586) have shown that the nickel catalyst containing more than 5% of alumina did not catalyse the hydrogenation of oil. It was shown that this inactivity was due to imperfect reduction of the catalyst. Evidently here alumina directly poisoned the reduction of nickel oxide and hence indirectly the hydrogenation. It also follows from the above cases that when a metallic surface is the catalyst, a partially reduced surface will be inactive or will possess

only a lower activity. Similarly where a lower oxide is the catalyst, a higher oxide will not be of much use and so on.

Fischer and his co-workers (*Brennstoff. Chem.*, 1933, 14, 64) got good nickel catalyst by carrying out reduction with a mixture of nitrogen and hydrogen in one case and ammonia and hydrogen in the other. Rogers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 49, 1432) showed that in presence of copper, zinc oxide was reduced to the metal at a temperature where it was not attacked when alone. Reduction of zinc oxide to zinc in presence of copper was also found by Frollich and his co-workers (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1929, 21, 109).

A nickel catalyst is generally known to catalyse reaction

We have also seen the inhibiting action of 5% alumina on the reduction of nickel catalyst in Armstrong's investigations cited before. The following investigation will show how far the promoters accelerate the chemical reactions that occur during the preparation of nickel catalyst and thereby indirectly its activity towards the above reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Nickel acetate was very carefully prepared so as to avoid, as far as practicable, the presence of any poison or promoter. A known quantity of the acetate with or without a promoter was dissolved in water and deposited on purified and ignited pumice (10-20 meshes). The dried product was then introduced inside a glass tube and was softly packed between two plugs of asbestos fibre. A thermometer was inserted inside the catalyst mass to read the temperature during the experiments. This tube containing the catalyst was then introduced into an electric resistance furnace. The catalyst was reduced in a current of hydrogen and next studied *in situ* with an 1:1 (by volume) mixture of carbon monoxide and hydrogen. The experimental details were practically the same as described in Part I of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 150).

Catalyst I : Pumice (17 g.), nickel acetate (3.5 g.).

Catalyst II : Pumice (17 g.), nickel acetate (3.5 g.), cerium nitrate (0.06 g.), vanadic acid* (0.04 g.).

Catalyst III : Pumice (17 g.), nickel acetate (3.5 g.), cerium nitrate (0.06 g.), chromium acetate (0.25 g.).

* Ammoniacal solution of 0.04 g. of vanadium pentoxide was used.

TABLE I.

Temp. of reduction = *300°.

Catalyst No.	Space velocity.	Vol. comp. of the resultant gas mixture.				Catalyst temp.	Remarks.
		CH ₄ .	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ .		
I	0.44	3%	0.25%	50.3%	46.2%	†370°	These experiments were repeated three times for confirmation
II	1.4	37.7	28.8	25.5	11.0	300	
III	2.7	44.9	30.7	17.7	7.3	„	

DISCUSSION.

From the data given in Table I, it is clear that nickel catalyst without any promoter is practically inert so far as the reaction

is concerned. Additions of promoters have increased the activity considerably. The point arises as to whether the promoters have got any direct beneficial effects on the above reaction.

Although all the catalysts were reduced at the same temperature, the colour of the pure nickel catalyst after reduction was grey-black with a greenish tinge. The colour of the promoted catalysts after reduction was black. This clearly indicates that the extent of reduction in case of pure nickel catalyst was less in comparison with those containing the promoters. Armstrong and Hilditch (*loc. cit.*) have shown that colour is black when the catalyst contains 80.7–44% of metallic nickel. It is grey-black when nickel present is 4.5%.

In the present investigation, the catalysts were not actually analysed to estimate the extent of reduction. For it was felt that such data, though valuable to get an idea regarding the average composition of the catalyst mass, do not indicate the correct composition of the surface. For it is not possible to analyse a surface. To get an idea regarding the nature of the surface, the catalyst material after its activity was studied with carbon monoxide and hydrogen mixture was allowed to cool in an atmosphere of this gas mixture. Nickel deposition was seen to occur only in case of the active catalysts. With a pure nickel preparation no such deposition occurred. Certainly sufficient metallic nickel particles were present on the catalyst surface containing promoters. The colour of the pure nickel

* No reaction occurred at 300°.

† The excess of hydrogen is due to that already present in the reaction tube.

catalyst combined with the analytical data of Armstrong and Hilditch and the fact that it did not form nickel carbonyl, clearly indicates that the surface was only partially reduced.

Schmidt (*Chem. Rev.*, 1933, 12, 371) has shown particularly in case of finely divided nickel (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 118, 216) that the progress of reduction is considerably hindered by sintering. Thereby inertness is produced and a part of the oxide remains unreacted upon. It is possible that the pure nickel catalyst was sintered in the intermediate stage and the promoters pushed the reduction to completion probably by stopping this sintering.

From the experimental data and what has been said above it cannot be said definitely whether the promoters had any direct accelerating influence upon the reaction

but it is clear that they helped a good deal, the process of reduction of the catalyst, thereby increasing the number of nickel particles on its surface.

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